

ETIOLOGY AND CAUSES OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Abstract: One of the most common causes of liver cirrhosis is V and hepatitis C infection. World Health Organization According to information, liver cirrhosis is a chronic liver disease is the last stage, diffuse fibrosis and normal structure of the liver changes its place with the formation of nodes. This article provides information about the causes, course and prevention of cirrhosis of the liver.

Keywords: Cirrhosis of the liver, clinical symptoms, diagnosis, elimination of causes, treatment.

The liver is one of the most important organs of the human body, it is the blood provides purification from toxins. In the digestive system of this organ, carbohydrates, actively participates in the metabolism of lipids and proteins. Any liver its malfunction has a negative effect on the whole body and the patient's life it is not surprising that it shows. Cirrhosis of the liver is a serious disease, as a result of which the liver tissues are replaced by connective tissue and the organ can perform its function stops. Cirrhosis of the liver is a chronic progressive disease that affects human life can lead to dangerous consequences. Liver cirrhosis is chronic liver is the final histological stage of a wide range of diseases: hepatocytes and damage to the protective mechanisms in the liver leads to regeneration and fibrosis. Chronic inflammatory diseases of the liver are different specialties attracting the attention of doctors more and more. This is chronic hepatitis related to the spread, cirrhosis is the last stage of hepatitis and death rate is high. The socio-economic significance of the disease is the ability to work it is also determined by the frequent spread of liver cirrhosis among people of age.

The processes taking place in the body are constantly dynamic are in balance, and their violation is imbalance and leads to disruption of homeostasis. homeostasis Biological agonist-antagonistic regulation of system functions homeostasis is a process of stabilizing the system and its necessary to adapt to changing conditions. If the system if it fails under the influence of a pathogenic factor, its balance is disturbed, which is similar to the processes of regulation of the function of hemostasis. In patients with liver failure, it is often simultaneous hypercoagulation, hypocoagulation and hyperfibrinolysis signs will be available. Suffered from cirrhosis Venous when a high rate of bleeding is observed in patients regular anticoagulant with heparin and vitamin K for thrombosis therapy is described. In

In addition, the treatment of cirrhosis of the liver is a complex task and its implementation requires large material costs. Therapeutic tactics for cirrhosis of the liver consists in treating the main disease that led to its development and eliminating complications therapy aimed at The ineffectiveness of these methods and the disease in cases of exacerbation, liver transplantation is indicated. Liver cirrhosis is a serious disease as a result of which liver tissue is replaced by connective tissue and the body ceases to perform its duties. According to literature, in Europe, as well as all patients with cirrhosis of the liver in former CIS countries more than half of the cases are related to alcohol consumption. However, a quarter of these patients were shown to have a history of hepatitis. Alcoholic along with drinks, viral hepatitis B, C, D (in liver pathology TTV- and The role of SEN viruses is being studied), metabolic diseases (hemochromatosis, Wilson Konovalov disease, alpha1-antitrypsin deficiency, metabolism-accumulation diseases), vascular diseases (Badd-Chiari syndrome), immunological factors (autoimmune hepatitis) and drugs.

In cases of cirrhosis of the liver, other treatment methods are the result if not, a liver transplant is required. Liver transplantation is a surgical intervention in which the damaged part of the organ is removed and its liver tissue taken from a healthy donor is transplanted instead. Liver transplantation to patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis it is recommended to be carried out, because in addition to the main disease, they have various there are visible complications. These complications include: internal and external complex blood discharges, accumulation of ascites fluid in the abdominal cavity, hepatorenal syndrome, liver encephalopathy, bacterial peritonitis. Conclusion: Therefore, in patients with liver cirrhosis, the disease is early the correct selection of diagnostic and treatment measures and the effectiveness of treatment helps to improve the quality of life of patients. Current liver in our country as well as in the whole world the widespread implementation of transplantation will bring hundreds of patients back to life is helping. But even in the early stages of the disease. There are several treatments that prevent it. The main recommendation: alcohol not to drink. It is necessary to follow a proper diet: fatty you should not eat food, chocolate, canned food, smoked food. The diet includes vitamins, fruits, plenty of liquid, dairy products, fat-free boiled meat should be included. It is necessary to eat small amounts 3-4 times a day. Following this diet, a person can protect himself from cirrhosis of the liver possible.

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